

G.A. 101084180 – NOVAFOODIES

Communication and dissemination activities WP6 – IT (Infoteam) – October 2024

Long version for Novafoodies website:

Bringing transparency to seafood with Novafoodies Mobile App

Go Infoteam, as part of the Novafoodies project, is launching an innovative mobile app aimed at helping consumers make more informed and sustainable choices when buying seafood. This app, set to be rolled out in pilot programs in Italy and Greece, will allow users to easily trace the journey of aquaculture products — *from farms to the fish stores* — by scanning a simple QR code.

With the Novafoodies Mobile App, European consumers will have access to critical information about the seafood they purchase, such as production certifications, transport conditions (including GPS location, temperature, and humidity). These conditions are monitored in real-time through IoT devices, which are designed and developed by ITENE, (WP Leader). This cutting-edge technology ensures precise data collection throughout the seafood supply chain. Moreover, blockchain technology is integrated to securely store and safeguard this data, ensuring its immutability and enhancing consumer trust in the reliability and authenticity of the information provided.

The app is designed to boost awareness around sustainable seafood consumption. By giving consumers easy access to traceability data, Novafoodies encourages more conscious decisions when buying seafood, promoting both sustainability and transparency within the industry.

Soon to be tested in Italy and Greece, the app will allow local producers to demonstrate their commitment to transparency and quality. This is just the beginning, with plans to expand across Europe, helping both consumers and the seafood industry embrace more sustainable practices.

Participating fish stores will display Novafoodies posters in Italian and Greek, inviting customers to download the app by scanning a QR code. The app will be available for both Android and iOS, making it easy for users to dive into a more transparent seafood market.

With the Novafoodies Mobile App, Go Infoteam is shaping a future where European consumers can trust the origins of their seafood and make choices that support sustainability.

Visit our landing page on: <https://landing.novafoodies.eu/>

Picture for website:

POSTER-NovafoodiesMarketPlaceMobileAPP-EN.png

Short version for Novafoodies social network:

Go Infoteam [LINK TO PROFILE URL] is proud to introduce the **Novafoodies** [LINK TO PROFILE URL] Mobile App, designed to bring transparency to the seafood supply chain. With blockchain and IoT technology, consumers can trace aquaculture products from production to fish stores by scanning a QR code.

Launching soon in pilot programs across Italy and Greece, this app supports sustainable choices by offering real-time traceability of seafood, ensuring trust and quality in every bite. Learn more and stay tuned for the full rollout across Europe.

#Seafood #Sustainability #Blockchain #IoT #SupplyChain #Transparency #Traceability
#GOinfoteam #Novafoodies #HorizonEurope

Picture for social network:

NovafoodiesMobileApp2.png

SOCIAL MEDIA	PROFILE URL
FACEBOOK	https://www.facebook.com/people/Gruppo-Goinfoteam/100066354648921/
LINKEDIN	https://www.linkedin.com/company/go-infoteam/mycompany/
TWITTER "X"	https://x.com/goinfoteam
INSTAGRAM	https://www.instagram.com/lifeatgoinfoteam/